

POPULATION DENSITY AND SOCIOECONOMIC GROWTH: CASE OF BANGLADESH

Syed Ferhat Anwar *

Abstract

Bangladesh has been delving on discovering her most unique brand promise. Over the years, Bangladesh has focused on language movement, liberation war; the largest delta, mangrove forest, sandy sea beach, etc. However, Bangladesh did not consider density by population size as one of the most unique brand promises. The obvious question is why should this be of importance? When we assess the role of density for a populace nation, in providing collective strength through efficient management of inclusive financing, attainment of effective distribution of electricity, competitive nature of labor force resulting in competitive wages, easy access to agricultural work place for multiple cultivation, reaching out for health care, and so on; it is evident that one of the major contributors of economic emancipation of the country perhaps could be population density resulting out of natural cluster creation. It is also interesting to note that when the major nations of the world such as the United States of America, India, United Kingdom, etc., are fighting for reverse migration and considering size of population as a threat to economic growth, Bangladesh with comparatively high-density profile, is doing well in economic growth. Therefore, it is pertinent to propose; if rising population density is sign of the things to come, then Bangladesh could be the perfect laboratory to design and prototype the future strategic directions for countries soon to have similar density ingredients. This paper is a conceptual undertaking to assess how Bangladesh could be transformed into a global brand focusing on becoming the seat of learning for the world to address the density paradox.

Keywords : *Brand Positioning, Paradox, Population Density, Provocation, Strategic Direction.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This concept paper is primarily based on the theoretical settings that somewhat two separate models in sociology argue that the level of population density in a human society has important social consequences. The structuralists, following an Emile Durkheimian point of view, see high population density, along with high population size, as a prerequisite for the development of division of labor as outlined by Theodore D Kemper (1975). On the other hand, behaviorally oriented followers such as Simmel, stress that, psychological and even physiological strain are outcome of dense living (Simmel George, 1971). Population density, defined as number of people living in a given geographical area has been of interest not only in terms of economic return from land but also in terms of social wellbeing (Yuri A Yegorov, 2009). It has been

* Professor, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

seen that population density is likely to play positive impact on economic growth, though negative impact in terms of pollution, corruption, and overall cost of public services are also observed (Ladd H, 1992). This paper is strictly limited to assessing the population density paradox for developing brand positioning of a nation.

Over the last decade, Bangladesh has been delving on discovering her most unique brand promise. Amongst many prospective ideas, that has stretched from culture to natural locations such as our language movement, the liberation war, the largest delta, the sandy sea beach, etc., it is interesting to note that Bangladesh did not consider density by population size as a brand promise. Ranking 'density of nations by most populous countries in the world', Bangladesh tops the list. The ranking of the top ten nations is depicted in table 1 below:

Table 1 : Top Ten Density Destination by Population Size (December 2018)

Rank	Country	Population	Density (pop/km ²)
1	Bangladesh	166,014,626	1,153
2	Taiwan	23,588,932	652
3	South Korea	51,635,256	515
4	Rwanda	12,001,136	456
5	Netherlands	17,297,088	417
6	Haiti	11,112,945	411
7	India	1,343,204,757	409
8	Israel	8,987,445	407
9	Burundi	10,681,186	384
10	Belgium	11,454,906	375

Source: WorldAtlas.com

The obvious question is why should this be of importance? In fact, politicians and economists have on various occasion considered this to be one of the major weaknesses of Bangladesh resulting in poverty. In fact, density along with size of population, as depicted in annexure 1, has been identified as one the major cause of corruption resulting out of limited land, higher costs of production, low health care, competition between housing, agriculture, and manufacturing, etc. Moreover, density has been blamed for malnutrition, disparity in education, huge unemployment or under employment, etc. In other words, in Bangladesh density was always equaled to scarcity (Amrita Dasgupta, 2007; Kabir M S, Seamoon F R, and Rahman M A, 2014).

However, when we assess the role of density for a populace nation, in providing collective strength through efficient management of inclusive financing, attainment of effective distribution of electricity, competitive nature of labor force resulting in competitive wages, easy access to agricultural work place for multiple cultivation, reaching out for health care, and so on; it is evident that one of the major contributors of economic emancipation of the country perhaps is population density. In this sense,

the opportunity is that population density means also social and economic proximity. One of the major success stories can be seen in case of Singapore, though they have a small population unlike Bangladesh.

Global studies on density and socio-economic impact clearly indicates that density does have both positive as well as negative impact. The illustration below depicts the financial elasticity of various factors due to approximately 10% increase in density.

Figure 1: Financial Elasticity of Variables Influencing Density (compiled from various literature)

The figure clearly supports the contention that density can have a both positive as well as negative impact on society and thus the paradox. However, Table 2 below explains that the impact is largely dependent on the overall management of how the society is attuned to follow standards of living while focusing on social, health, economic, and behavioral dimensions. Figure 1 and Table 2, together, clearly explain that it is likely that density can be turned into an opportunity. However, if such care in any one of the dimensions is ignored, it can be devastating. Thus, one may conclude that density could be an opportunity for a better living and brand positioning, thus it is important that the world looks closely at this future dimension which perhaps cannot be ignored. It is even more important, under the recent Corona Pandemic that the world assesses the implication of density as the global density increases.

Table 2 : Variables Influencing Density Paradox

	Variable	Impact of Variable on Density	Reference
1	Wages	Positive; cluster causes morphological density, due to agglomeration	Andersson et al., 2016; Grump, 2010
2	Rental	Negative; when land scarce and higher level of demand supply gap	Ahlfeldt et al., 2015

	Variable	Impact of Variable on Density	Reference
3	Innovation Intensity	Positive; due to fulfillment of wants that are resulting out of cluster interaction	Carlino et al., 2007
4	Travel Distance	Ambiguous; can reach destination easily, however, traffic congestion may create some negative impact	Yang et al., 2015
5	Vehicle Speed	Ambiguous; depends on type of vehicle, stoppage, and cost of speed	Pouyanne, 2004
6	Consumption Value	Positive; due to clustering of services and expected belief that people will not travel far due to traffic	Cervero & Kockelman, 1997
7	Local public Spending	Ambiguous; service quality a detriment, density may decrease footprint, purchasing power plays a role, however, economies of scales likely to play a positive impact	Ahlfeldt et al., 2015
8	Crime Rates	Negative; likely to have higher crime rates like petty theft. More if disparity in cluster high and distance between cluster low	Chauvin et al., 2016
9	Open space Bio Diversity	Negative; higher the density lower the chance of open space and less bio diversity	Ahlfeldt & Pietrostefani, 2016
10	Roof Space	Positive; clusters result in easy monitoring of roof top economic activity be it roof top agriculture or solar energy options, etc.	Liu et al., 2014
11	Environmental Impact	Ambiguous; carbon and other emissions are likely to be compact and thus dense resulting in higher air pollution, however, if proper environmental management is maintained, may result in higher recycling opportunities having a positive impact, in addition, some people may move into more personalized vehicle such as cycle since distance.	Albouy & Stuart, 2016
12	Energy consumption	Positive; clusters result in lower transmission costs and greater efficiency	Glaeser & Kahn, 2010

	Variable	Impact of Variable on Density	Reference
13	Public transportation	Positive; prospect of public transportation increases with density due to demand for mass transportation, resulting in lesser number of self-driven transport	Duranton & Turner, 2015
14	Income inequality	Ambiguous; disparity may arise due to income and professional level, but it is expected that the disparity will gradually decline over time with trade and information regarding each other due to ease in communications	Couture, 2016
15	Mortality impact	Ambiguous; impact of mortality is related to two aspects, first is higher emission will result in higher mortality but more physical activity such as cycling will reduce mortality plus energy efficiency	Merlo et al., 2006
16	Susceptible to Disease	Negative; one of the major negative aspect of density is contagious disease that may result in epidemic within that society due to the nature of the disease, which may result in psychological depression	Andreae Barrios, 2018; Richard Bruns, 2019
17	Subjective wellbeing	Ambiguous; wellbeing depends on other factors and thus one cannot clearly outline the impact, however, it is suggested that people in general do not like too dense a population	Glaeser et al., 2016 Moazzami et al., 2020
	NET Impact	If society is made to follow certain standards of living with focus on social, health, economic, and behavioral dimensions, it is likely that density can be turned into an opportunity. However, if care in any one of the dimensions is ignored, it can be devastating.	

The next obvious question could be why should the world take this into cognizance? The answer is obvious. One of the major concerns for the world is population growth resulting in land becoming the scarcest resource; the ultimate non-human economic resource for mankind. It is this land which provides for food, mineral resources, water, energy, and so forth. Thus, tomorrow's world will strive for efficient use of land in one form and productivity enhancement through use of technology for the two most important economic resource, people and land. The ultimate purpose is of course better living for the humanity. Moreover, estimates indicate that if population management is not undertaken with a strategic intent, it may result in catastrophe. This could be due to economic, civil disobedience, or even regional warfare all magnified by increasing signs of environmental stress. One of the most obvious places could be Africa, which by many measures is occupying one of the most important status in the global manifestation. The projections in population growth for the years 2050 and 2100 for top ten nations is projected in table 3 below.

Table 3 : Population Projection Year 2050 and 2100

Rank	Country	Population (2050)	Rank	Country	Population (2100)
1	India	1.66 bn	1	India	1.5bn
2	China	1.41 bn	2	China	1.0bn
3	Nigeria	410.64m	3	Nigeria	794m
4	USA	389.59m	4	USA	447m
5	Indonesia	321.55m	5	DR Congo	379m
6	Pakistan	306.94m	6	Pakistan	352m
7	Brazil	232.69m	7	Indonesia	306m
8	Bangladesh	201.93m	8	Tanzania	304m
9	DR Congo	197.40m	9	Ethiopia	250m
10	Ethiopia	190.87m	10	Uganda	214m

Source: World Economic Forum 2019

The world population parameters will however vary based on the population growth rates one of such projection is provided in the figure 2 below.

Figure 2: World Population 1900-2050 (projected from various sources)

The above data indicates that population growth is likely to affect the global population density concerns and hence it is important that we assess the issue pertaining to population density management as a key factor driving national plans in the future. It is therefore essential that the world starts to understand how density can be managed properly to be able to provide guidance for growth. One other important point needs to be flagged. It is evident from the projections provided in table 3 depicting population of 2100 that Africa and Asia are likely to be the area where density management will be of utmost necessity. Thus, it is important that plans be made to address the ever-alarming scenario in one of the most contentious regions on earth.

2. BANGLADESH PARADOX

The case of microfinance in Bangladesh is a good example of how density led operations directly and indirectly provided major policy and material support to make it probably the largest microfinance sector in the world. This was primarily due to easy access to larger group of population resulting in easy creation of group lending and at the same time ease in monitoring (Dewan A H Alamgir, 2009). The availability of labor cluster for manufacturing such as RMG is another example. Clusters compete for job at a lower cost (Anonymous, 2016) since they are not just aware of what is happening in the neighborhood, but at the same time, word of mouth travels fast. Primary health campaigns have been successful since female field workers were picked from the community and could reach large populations in no time while continuing to undertake their own household chores (Bappy Rahman, 2017). The success of Union Digital Centers is perhaps another example of how density can make services not just more social advancement but also more economically feasible (TIB Report, 2017). These practices show that population density by far is not a developmental curse, but an enormous opportunity once relevant institutional infrastructure is in place to harness social proximity and networking effects. The paradox is that though Bangladesh is far more densely populated country compared

to her neighbors, it betters in life expectancy at birth, though high density resulting in greater competition for food and nutrition in a less developed country may result in lower life expectancy at birth (WHO Report, 2019).

3. STRATEGIC DIRECTION

If rising population density is sign of the things to come, question is, could Bangladesh be the laboratory to design and prototype the future strategic directions for countries soon to have similar density centric challenges? Indeed, Bangladesh could be considered as one of the major examples in the world which is dense enough to assess issues pertaining to density and the application of new development path laid out for the world. On the other hand, Bangladesh also fulfills the requirement for the new technology to work on. Furthermore, programs like A2I (Access to Information) demonstrate to what extent embrace of technology and experimental mindset can be transformative for development (Naimur Rahman, Salahuddin M Aminuzzaman, and Nazneen Ahmed, 2019). In what follows I would like to put forward some provocative issues as to how this tentative experimentation agenda can inform the future regional and global strategies to harness opportunities stemming from population density. I believe that we capitalize this unique trait of Bangladesh to shed light on the possible future of rest of the world and assess what the world should plan for her citizens. This essentially will result in a unique brand positioning for Bangladesh.

Provocation 1: Bangladesh, and by the same token other densely populated countries with high tech penetration, should become hotbed of testing and invalidating descriptive and predictive powers of big data analytics. At the same time, this is the place where ethical and sensitivities around data use will come at the forefront and will need to be dealt with. Indeed, big data analytics is likely to be one of the major research methodologies of the future. Data analytics include datamining, which involves sorting through large datasets to identify trends, patterns and relationships; predictive analytics, which seeks to predict customer behavior, equipment failures and other future events; and machine learning, an artificial intelligence technique, etc. It is important to note that the four most important factors for efficient data analytics includes as outlined by experts are as follows (Javier et al., 2015).

Volume: Terabytes, records, distribution, etc.

Velocity: Batch, processes, streams, etc.

Value: Statistical, events, hypothetical, etc.

Variability: Changes, linkages, dynamics, etc.

Veracity: Trustworthiness, authenticity, origins, etc.

Variety: Structured, unstructured, multifactor, etc.

Clearly, Bangladesh could be at the center of experimenting the use of big data and assessing the validity, reliability, and sensitivity of transforming data into information and ultimately into strategic intervention.

Provocation 2: The availability of data will allow us to zoom into the ways social non-digital interaction contributes to transformation of culture in the country. Cluster analysis using social interaction and cultural development is likely to be the next important dimension to look at. The measure of formation of culture looks at shifts in the living status of individuals in society taking into consideration the cosmopolitan and global interaction between culture and adaptability of cultures within the society. This requires studies of clusters that have enough data points. The cluster studies on the other hand require having first a homogenous group large enough to be able to undertake predictive judgment. In addition, to make cluster analysis meaningful, longitudinal shifts of population through economic, behavioral shifts, and social growth needs to be studied (Christian H M Ketels, 2013). This can be undertaken through studies of the social network having high traffic. Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh has one of the highest Facebook densities in the world (Digital Marketing Report 2017). It is obvious that any study centering around cluster can be best undertaken in Bangladesh and for urban analytics, in the capital city of Bangladesh, Dhaka.

Provocation 3: Abundance of data entries amidst high density population will allow us to test new approaches to data security and digital accountability. The third dimension to be considered for the future technological use under an extreme density driven society is security of individuals in the society and thus traceability of information of source. This is doable using block chains. The efficiency of block chain technology is not only important for traceability, but also economic transaction and perhaps even communications. Bangladesh is again well placed to assess use of block chain technology and test the efficiency of its use for security, trade and commerce and to eventually go beyond that (Reshma Kamath, 2018). The sub-sectors to focus on include retail, finance (including micro finance), customs, land, education etc. Again, Bangladesh is demographically one of the best places for developing business model around block chain for the simple reason that it can help unwind the complexity of relationship and thus bring efficiency in traceability.

Provocation 4: High data density can offset public health challenges in emerging economies through bio-informatics. Indeed, bio-informatics for predicting health and aiding in designing pharmacodynamics. This is essential to not only aid in building future drugs but above all to ensure that the world has faith on health science that will ensure better living through managing population growth. It is obvious that health will continue to be at the top most agenda in the world. Moreover, according to WHO (2019) Bangladesh in terms of life expectancy at birth (72.66 years) even with her high population density has performed even better compared to India (68.83 years) and Pakistan (66.53 years). Furthermore, Bangladesh also has a strong pharmaceutical industry as well as primary health care records and thus, Bangladesh could be a good experimental ground for assessing health parameters focusing on bio-informatics which is getting immense global attention for various health remedies (Jane A Leopold and Joseph Loscalzo, 2018).

Provocation 5: Robotics is likely to replace humans in activities that are categorized as dangerous, dirty, and dull for the human to take interest in. Thus, any job requiring low level of skills and creativity is likely to fall under this definition. Bangladesh, housing one of the most low-cost labor in the world, again could be a perfect place to assess how this replacement should be designed to ensure smooth transfer that should focus on productivity as a bottom line but more importantly, for skills prediction, future education design and employment agenda (Joerg Mayer, 2018).

Provocation 6: Recent studies on health (Andreae Barrios 2018 and Richard Bruns, 2019) by organizations such as World Economic Forum, Johns Hopkins University, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and Rockefeller Foundation have clearly indicated that it is highly likely that an endemic will strike the world with brutal force, it is evident that under such circumstances, countries with higher density will be affected more. Now, the pandemic is no more a projection but a reality as Corona Pandemic strikes the world and the entire world is seriously in crises. Initial studies are clearly indicating that population density is one of the major factors, in one side contributing to increasing the infection through contact; while at the same time, ensures faster communication of information and thus restrains infection (Nicholas et al., 2020 and Sam et al., 2020). Therefore, it is imperative that studies be undertaken in countries such as Bangladesh to not just assess the impact but more importantly devise mechanism to fight such health disaster.

Provocation 7: SDG test case is perhaps the other focus that Bangladesh can be an experimental ground for the world to understand the application of SDG agenda under extreme case of population density. It is evident that positive empowering of population solutions is key to meeting the agenda set by SDG. With high population density, per-capita availability of resources centering around one of the major factors, i.e. land, is reduced (less food resulting in hunger and wellbeing, challenge in clean water sanitation, stress on decent work environment, etc.), which automatically is likely to have an impact on attainment of SDG. Bangladesh has not done essentially well in achieving the various goals but has performed better compared to some, including her neighbors. However, it will be interesting to assess the performance through pilots of clusters focusing on all the goals. Since the indicators and measures are still under experimentation, as outlined in the 2018 SDG Index and dashboard report, it is obvious, that further changes will be required prior to finalizing the strategic action plan. Bangladesh with the high population density and sitting at the boarder of lower income and developing category should be a perfect place for such experimentation (Wolfgang Lutz, 2016). Furthermore, Bangladesh has also performed well in applying CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) strategic intervention tagged with other charity (including religious and donor driven) models, thus, once again for any sustainable model building Bangladesh could be perfect ground because of her density dividend.

4. CONCLUSION

The above discussion outlines some of the roles the thinking hubs may play to help Bangladesh focus on a more scientific undertaking for her growth plan, while at the same time help the world understand how to manage population density of the future for economic and social emancipation through using experimental models in Bangladesh as a test case. Thus, it will be interesting to assess the role of density as a dividend rather than a threat for populations across the world. One must keep in mind that the focus is here to take advantage from the density rather than sway away by the threats. This paper has not investigated other parameters and thus can be left for future research. To be able to develop a conclusive model, it will require thorough and focused studies in multiple locations of the world to be able to draw a global development map focusing on density as a dividend rather than a threat or as some want to believe a curse. The discussion above clearly outlines the unique brand positioning of Bangladesh, being the most densely populated country in the world when considering the countries with large population. Therefore, when the major countries of the world are considering 'negative migration' as the strategy to tackle problems resulting out of population density, Bangladesh can help the world to assess possible strategic directions to address this burning issue.

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